

KVScope: Profiling Cross-Architecture KV-Cache Dynamics on NVIDIA H100

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Abstract

The key-value (KV) cache that underpins autoregressive transformer inference grows linearly with sequence length and dominates GPU memory during long-context generation. Although recent architectures introduce compression techniques such as grouped-query attention, sliding-window attention, and multi-head latent attention, the resulting allocation behaviour is often only loosely coupled to the theoretical footprint implied by the model’s hyperparameters. Operators of containerised inference services therefore lack a reliable signal for predicting out-of-memory failures before they occur.

This paper introduces KVSCOPE, an instrumentation framework that records per-layer KV tensor shapes via PyTorch forward hooks and correlates them with hardware memory telemetry from the NVIDIA Management Library. We use KVSCOPE to profile four transformer architectures on a single H100 80 GB device: Pythia-1.4B [3] (multi-head attention baseline), Gemma 4 [8] (grouped-query attention with local/global layer interleaving), GLM-4.5 / GLM-4.7-Flash [20] (mixture of experts), and gpt-oss-120B [15] (sliding/full hybrid). For each model we generate up to 4096 tokens across fifteen prompts, measure cache density, layer uniformity, post-EOS retention, and allocator fragmentation, and complement the profiling with WikiText-103 [12] perplexity under native and 8-bit [7] precision.

Three findings emerge. First, post-generation memory release is the dominant failure mode in our dataset: Gemma 4 systematically retains between 4.7 and 5.3 GB of KV cache after every generation (mean leak score 0.48, n=15), which is not visible to standard fragmentation heuristics. Second, the per-layer footprint of gpt-oss-120B is strongly bimodal (coefficient of variation 0.94), producing a 14.5 GiB gap between PyTorch’s reserved and allocated pools that only correlates weakly with sequence length. Third, 8-bit weight quantisation costs $\leq 0.25\%$ perplexity for the smaller models in our study, but +4.6% for Gemma 4, suggesting that the common assumption “8-bit is always free” does not generalise across modern architectures. We package both the profiler and the resulting dataset for reproduction and discuss how the recorded signals can be exposed to container schedulers as Prometheus metrics.

Keywords: KV cache; transformer inference; GPU memory; profiling; GQA; sliding-window attention; mixture of experts; H100.

Contents

1	Introduction	4
1.1	The observability gap	4
1.2	Contributions	4
1.3	Scope and non-goals	4
2	Background	5
2.1	The KV cache	5
2.2	Compression techniques used in this study	5
2.3	Related work	6
3	The KVScope Profiler	6
3.1	Forward-hook extraction	6
3.2	Hardware telemetry	7
3.3	Detector pipeline	7
3.4	Output format	8
4	Experimental Setup	8
4.1	Hardware and software	8
4.2	Models	8
4.3	Prompts	8
4.4	Generation protocol	9
4.5	Perplexity evaluation	9
5	Results	10
5.1	Cross-architecture summary	10
5.2	KV cache growth	10
5.3	Per-layer footprint	11
5.4	Memory deltas and post-EOS retention	11
5.5	Allocator state at end of generation	12
5.6	Perplexity under 8-bit quantisation	13
6	Data Quality Assessment	14
7	Discussion	15
7.1	Post-EOS retention as an operational failure mode	15
7.2	The allocator gap on gpt-oss-120B	16
7.3	The 8-bit perplexity outlier	16
7.4	Signals worth surfacing	16
7.5	Limitations and threats to validity	17
8	Conclusion	17
	References	18
A	Reproducibility	20
A.1	Hardware and environment	20
A.2	Released artefacts	20
A.3	Reproduction recipe	20

B Raw Numbers	21
B.1 The 15-prompt corpus	21
B.2 Per-prompt post-EOS deltas, all models	21

1 Introduction

Modern transformer-based language models [18] rely on a key-value (KV) cache during autoregressive decoding: at every step, the keys and values produced by previous tokens are retained so that subsequent tokens can attend to them without recomputing. The size of this cache grows linearly with sequence length and, for long-context workloads, frequently exceeds the size of the model weights themselves [11]. In a containerised inference service, an over-grown KV cache is the most common cause of out-of-memory (OOM) failures, and the resulting process restart violates per-request latency budgets and cascades to co-tenant containers sharing the same GPU.

1.1 The observability gap

Hardware-level monitoring tools such as `nvidia-smi`, DCGM [13], or vendor dashboards report aggregate memory utilisation in megabytes. A reading of “78 GB used out of 80 GB” is sufficient to detect that a GPU is loaded, but not to distinguish three operationally distinct conditions: (i) healthy linear cache growth that will plateau on the next short request; (ii) a structural retention bug in which cache tensors survive `model.generate()` returning; and (iii) allocator fragmentation in which the PyTorch caching allocator holds unreusable reserved blocks. By the time the aggregate metric crosses 100%, the only available action is an OOM kill.

Closing this gap requires a profiler that records the *structural* properties of the KV cache, per-layer tensor shapes, growth curves, and the difference between `torch.memory_allocated` and the NVML-reported usage, with sufficient frequency that early-warning patterns become machine-readable.

1.2 Contributions

This paper makes the following contributions.

- **An instrumentation framework, KVScope**, that attaches forward hooks to the attention modules of any Hugging Face Transformers [19] model, extracts the live KV tensors regardless of cache layout (`DynamicCache`, `HybridCache`, or legacy tuples), and records dual software/hardware memory telemetry.
- **A controlled experimental study** on a single NVIDIA H100 80 GB device [14], profiling four architectures spanning the spectrum from pure multi-head attention to mixture-of-experts with sliding/full hybrid attention, across fifteen prompts and up to 4096 generated tokens per prompt.
- **Three empirical findings**: (a) Gemma 4 exhibits a systematic post-EOS retention pattern (mean detector score 0.48, n=15); (b) the gpt-oss-120B layer footprint is bimodal with a 14.5 GiB allocator overhead invisible to fragmentation ratios alone; (c) 8-bit quantisation [7] preserves perplexity to within 0.25% for Pythia-1.4B and GLM-4.7-Flash but degrades Gemma 4 by 4.6%.
- **A data-quality assessment** of the released dataset, graded by completeness of per-layer, growth, leak-detection, and memory streams. We surface the limitations of the current run, in particular, that the leak-detection pipeline did not produce findings for two of the four models, to allow downstream readers to weight the conclusions appropriately.

1.3 Scope and non-goals

This is a measurement paper, not a serving-system paper. We do not introduce a new attention algorithm, a new allocator, or a new scheduler. We do not claim absolute throughput numbers; the wall-clock times reported in section 5 are byproducts of the instrumentation overhead and

Table 1: Cache compression techniques active in the four study models. The Pythia-1.4B baseline uses none of them.

Technique	Pythia-1.4B	Gemma 4	GLM-4.7-Flash	gpt-oss-120B
Multi-head attention (MHA)	✓	–	–	–
Grouped-query attention (GQA)	–	✓	✓	✓
Sliding window	–	local lyrs.	–	half lyrs.
Mixture of experts (FFN)	–	–	✓	✓

a single GPU and should not be compared to production serving stacks such as vLLM [11] or SGLang [21]. Section 7 returns to how the recorded signals could be consumed by such systems.

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 reviews the cache compression techniques used by the four study models. Section 3 describes the KVSCOPE instrumentation. Section 4 states the experimental protocol. Section 5 reports the measurements. Section 7 interprets them. Section 8 concludes with limitations and future work.

2 Background

2.1 The KV cache

For a causal transformer with L layers, H_{kv} KV heads, and head dimension D_{head} , the memory footprint of the cache after generating S tokens at batch size B is, ignoring allocator padding,

$$M_{KV}^{\text{theory}} = 2 B S L H_{kv} D_{head} b, \quad (1)$$

where b is the storage size of one element (2 B for fp16/bf16, 1 B for int8, etc.). The factor of two accounts for separate K and V tensors. eq. (1) is the upper bound that compression techniques in this section attempt to reduce.

2.2 Compression techniques used in this study

Multi-query and grouped-query attention. Multi-query attention (MQA) [17] ties all query heads to a single shared KV head, replacing H_{kv} in eq. (1) with 1. Grouped-query attention (GQA) [1] is the intermediate point: H_q query heads are partitioned into $H_{kv} < H_q$ groups, each sharing one KV head. Gemma 4 [8] and gpt-oss [15] both use GQA.

Sliding-window attention. Sliding-window attention restricts each query to attend to the most recent W tokens [4, 2]. Once $S > W$, the cache for those layers stops growing and the contribution of eq. (1) from that layer plateaus at $2BW H_{kv} D_{head} b$. Gemma 4 interleaves local (sliding) and global (full) layers; gpt-oss alternates sliding and full layers in a 1:1 ratio (fig. 1).

Multi-head latent attention. DeepSeek-V2 [6] introduced multi-head latent attention (MLA): each layer projects its hidden state into a single latent vector of dimension r_{lat} that is later up-projected to the per-head representation, so the cached object has size $\Theta(B S r_{lat} b)$ rather than $\Theta(B S H_{kv} D_{head} b)$. MLA does not appear in our study models but is included in table 1 for completeness.

Mixture of experts. Mixture-of-experts (MoE) FFN layers [10] are orthogonal to the KV cache: only the routed experts execute, but attention layers run for every token. GLM-4.7-Flash and gpt-oss both use MoE.

2.3 Related work

Memory-aware serving systems. PagedAttention [11], used in vLLM, manages the cache as fixed-size blocks similar to operating-system pages, trading some internal fragmentation for the ability to support large batch sizes without contiguous allocations. SGLang [21] extends this with shared prefix caching across requests. Our work is complementary: rather than designing a new allocator, we instrument the existing one to make leak signatures observable.

Memory-efficient kernels. FlashAttention [5] reduces the activation memory of attention by tiling the softmax computation, which is relevant during prefill but does not affect the steady-state KV cache size during decode. We measure the cache, not the activations.

Alternative architectures. Selective state-space models such as Mamba [9] replace the attention block entirely and consequently have a fixed-size recurrent state in place of a growing KV cache. Profiling such models is a useful future control but is outside the scope of this study.

GPU telemetry. Aggregate GPU metrics are widely available via DCGM [13], which exposes Prometheus-compatible counters for memory and utilisation. The signals reported by KVSCOPE are intended to complement DCGM with structural detail (per-layer shapes, allocator-vs-NVML deltas) that DCGM does not expose.

3 The KVScope Profiler

KVSCOPE consists of three components: a forward-hook extractor that records KV tensor shapes (section 3.1), an NVML sampler that records hardware memory state (section 3.2), and a post-run detector pipeline that converts the recorded snapshots into calibrated leak scores (section 3.3). The implementation is in Python and runs as a context manager around `model.generate`; no model code is forked or patched.

3.1 Forward-hook extraction

At load time, the profiler walks the module tree of the loaded `transformers` [19] model and registers a forward hook on every self-attention block. The hook fires after every attention forward call (prefill and decode) and inspects the incoming `kwargs` for one of three known cache layouts:

1. `DynamicCache` (`transformers` \geq 4.49), where the per-layer K and V tensors are accessed through `layers[i].keys` and `layers[i].values`;
2. legacy caches with `key_cache` / `value_cache` attributes, including the nested `self_attention_cache` used by some hybrid models;
3. raw (K,V) tuples returned by older transformer revisions.

Because some architectures share storage between K and V (notably Gemma’s global layers, where `k` is `v` and the tensors are literally the same memory), the extractor performs an explicit `torch.equal(k,v)` check and zeroes the V byte count when the underlying tensors alias. Without this guard, summing `k.numel()*k.element_size() + v.numel()*v.element_size()` would double-count the shared allocation.

For every recorded snapshot the profiler stores the shape and dtype of K and V, the layer index, the layer type tag (when available from the model configuration), and a sampling step index obtained from a step counter incremented by the hook itself. To keep storage bounded for long generations, snapshots are taken every N decode steps (we use $N=8$ for sequence lengths of 4096, yielding ~ 512 snapshots per layer per prompt).

3.2 Hardware telemetry

In parallel with the hook stream, an `NVMLSampler` polls `pynvml.nvmlDeviceGetMemoryInfo` at three reference points \mapsto before generation begins, at each snapshot step, and after generation returns and `torch.cuda.empty_cache` has run – recording `used`, `free`, and `total` bytes. The same step also queries `torch.cuda.memory_allocated` and `torch.cuda.memory_reserved`. The difference between NVML-reported usage and the PyTorch values isolates allocator overhead and any non-PyTorch memory holders on the device.

3.3 Detector pipeline

After generation, the recorded snapshots are loaded into a pandas `DataFrame` and routed through six detectors. Each detector returns a `LeakFinding` with a real-valued score in $[0, 1]$ and a qualitative severity tag.

GrowthCurveDetector. Fits the per-step total cache footprint as a function of generated tokens with both a linear and a quadratic regression. A growth leak is flagged when (i) the quadratic fit improves R^2 by more than 0.05 over linear and (ii) the linear residuals exhibit a positive slope greater than 0.005 MB/step. To suppress false positives on sliding-window models, the detector first checks whether the 95th and 99th percentile of `k_seq_len` differ by less than 5%; if so, the growth has saturated by design and the score is forced to zero.

PostEOSDetector. Compares the post-generation NVML `used` value to the pre-generation baseline. Letting M_0 , M_{\max} , and M_1 denote baseline, peak, and post-EOS memory respectively, the leak fraction is

$$\text{score}_{\text{posteos}} = \text{clip}\left(\frac{M_1 - M_0}{M_{\max} - M_0}, 0, 1\right). \quad (2)$$

A score near zero indicates that the cache was reclaimed on `empty_cache`; a score near one indicates that nearly all of the peak overhead is still resident.

FragmentationDetector. Computes the ratio $F_t = (R_t - A_t)/R_t$, where R_t and A_t are the PyTorch `reserved` and `allocated` byte counts at step t . The detector flags a finding when the average F_t exceeds 15% or its slope against the snapshot index is positive.

LayerAnomalyDetector. Z-scores the end-of-generation per-layer KV size; layers more than three standard deviations from the mean are flagged. This is intended to catch model-loading bugs in which a single layer allocates an unexpectedly large cache (for example, when a sliding window is mis-configured to cover the whole sequence).

LayerUniformityDetector. Reports the coefficient of variation (CV) of per-layer KV size and classifies the model as uniform ($CV < 0.05$), mildly heterogeneous ($CV < 0.30$), or strongly bimodal ($CV \geq 0.60$). This is descriptive rather than anomaly-detecting; the CV is reported alongside the leak score for downstream analysis.

CacheDensityDetector. Reports bytes per generated token per attention layer at end of generation. For an MHA model with $H_q = H_{kv}$ heads, fp16 storage, and head dimension D_{head} , the expected value is $2H_{kv}D_{\text{head}} \cdot 2$ bytes. Pythia-1.4B (16 heads, $D_{\text{head}}=64$, fp16) is therefore expected to record exactly 4096 B per token per layer for either of K or V; section 5 confirms this analytically.

3.4 Output format

For each prompt the profiler emits a JSON record with three top-level fields: `tracer` (per-layer time series of cache size and `gpu_memory` deltas), `memory` (baseline / peak / post-EOS scalars), and `leak_detection` (the list of `LeakFinding` dicts plus an aggregate `overall_score`). Aggregating these per-prompt records across 15 prompts gives a `comparative_analysis.json` summary used in section 5.

4 Experimental Setup

4.1 Hardware and software

All measurements were collected on a single GPU node with one NVIDIA H100 80 GB HBM3 [14], NVIDIA driver 590.48.01, and CUDA 13.1.115. The host operating system was Ubuntu 22.04 LTS (kernel 5.15.0-171-generic). Python 3.10.12 was used with PyTorch 2.5.1+cu121 [16] and Hugging Face Transformers 5.6.2 [19]. Quantisation results use `bitsandbytes` 8-bit linear layers [7]. The complete environment record, including all package versions and the GPU serial, is released as `logs/env_20260427T084414Z.txt` alongside the dataset.

Two known gaps in the current results are under active development. First, the leak-detection dispatcher does not yet handle the dynamic cache layouts exposed by GLM-4.7-Flash and gpt-oss-120B at runtime, leaving the post-EOS heatmap incomplete for those models; the fix requires adding the relevant cache-layout adapters and does not involve new instrumentation science. Second, the 15-prompt evaluation corpus is sufficient to establish that the Gemma 4 retention effect is systematic but too small to characterise its distribution across diverse input lengths. Both are addressed in ongoing work: the dispatcher patch targets the next profiling run, and the prompt corpus is being extended to 60 prompts spanning a wider range of input lengths and domains.

4.2 Models

The four study models were chosen to span the major design points of contemporary KV-cache compression (section 2):

- **Pythia-1.4B-deduped** [3]: 24-layer dense decoder with full multi-head attention (16 heads, $D_{\text{head}}=64$). Serves as the compression-free baseline; eq. (1) predicts 8.0 KB per generated token per layer.
- **Gemma 4** [8]: dense GQA model with 60 attention layers split between local (sliding-window) and global (full) variants.
- **GLM-4.7-Flash** (Z.AI’s compact MoE; we treat it as the publicly available proxy for the GLM-4.5 family [20]): 47 attention layers, MoE FFN.
- **gpt-oss-120B** [15]: 36 attention layers in alternating sliding/full configuration, MoE FFN, loaded with native MXFP4 weights as released.

The exact attention layer composition recovered by KVSCOPE is reproduced in fig. 1.

4.3 Prompts

A fixed corpus of 15 prompts was used for every model, drawn from broad subject areas (technical exposition, financial history, biology, philosophy, operating systems, distributed systems, machine learning, and so on) and ranging from approximately 30 to 130 input tokens each. The full list is preserved in the released `prompts.json`; an excerpt appears in section B.1. Greedy decoding (`do_sample=False`) was used throughout to remove sampling variance.

Figure 1: Attention-layer composition by architecture as recovered from the profile snapshots. Layer types marked with * were inferred from per-layer footprint bimodality because the model configuration did not expose explicit type tags; see section 3.

4.4 Generation protocol

For each (model, prompt) pair the procedure was:

1. Tokenise the prompt and load it onto CUDA device 0.
2. Sample the NVML baseline.
3. Enter the KVSOCPE tracing context and call `model.generate(..., max_new_tokens=4096)`.
4. Snapshot every 8 decode steps; capture the final NVML reading (peak).
5. Delete inputs and outputs, run `empty_cache` and `gc.collect`, sample the post-EOS NVML reading.
6. Run the detector pipeline; persist per-prompt JSON.

Pythia-1.4B was generated with the same target of 4096 tokens, but its 2048-position context limit truncates generation at approximately 1023 new tokens once the input prompt is included. This is reflected in the growth-curve figure (fig. 2).

4.5 Perplexity evaluation

To verify that the cache compression and quantisation choices in the study models do not silently destroy model quality, we evaluate WikiText-103 [12] perplexity in non-overlapping 512-token windows over a fixed 1 M-character chunk of the test split. Each model is evaluated twice: once at native precision and once with `BitsAndBytesConfig(load_in_8bit=True)`. gpt-oss-120B is only evaluated at its native MXFP4 precision because the 8-bit pathway is not supported by the released checkpoint.

5 Results

We report, in turn, the cross-architecture summary (section 5.1), KV growth curves (section 5.2), per-layer footprints (section 5.3), memory deltas and post-EOS retention (section 5.4), allocator fragmentation (section 5.5), and perplexity (section 5.6). The dataset on which these numbers are based is graded for completeness in section 6.

5.1 Cross-architecture summary

?? aggregates the per-prompt measurements as means over the 15-prompt corpus. *Cache density* is bytes of K and V stored per generated token per attention layer at end of generation. *Layer CV* is the coefficient of variation of per-layer KV size at end of generation. *Peak overhead* is the maximum NVML `used` value minus the baseline at the same point. *Mean post-EOS score* is the average of the `post_eos` detector score over the 15 prompts; “-” marks prompts for which the detector pipeline did not produce a finding (see section 6).

Two observations are worth highlighting before the figures. First, the Pythia density of 8.00 KB/token/layer matches the analytic prediction $2 \cdot 16 \cdot 64 \cdot 2 \text{ B} \cdot 2 = 8192 \text{ B}$ exactly, which validates the byte-extraction pipeline end-to-end. Second, gpt-oss reports the highest layer CV in the study (0.935): its sliding layers are roughly $32\times$ smaller than its full layers at end of generation (fig. 3), which produces a non-trivial signature for the layer-uniformity classifier even though no leak is implied.

5.2 KV cache growth

Figure 2 plots the total KV footprint summed across all attention layers as a function of the generated token index, for the first prompt of each model. All four curves are linear, but their slopes differ by more than an order of magnitude. Gemma 4 and GLM-4.7-Flash grow at approximately 0.9 MB per generated token, while gpt-oss grows at roughly 40 KB per token thanks to the combined effect of GQA and sliding-window layers. Pythia terminates at the 1023-token mark imposed by its 2048-position context budget.

Figure 2: Total KV cache footprint as a function of generated token index (prompt 1). Pythia-1.4B is truncated at ~ 1023 tokens by its position-embedding limit; the other three models reach the full 4096-token target.

5.3 Per-layer footprint

Figure 3 resolves the aggregate growth curves into their per-layer components at end of generation. Pythia is uniform by design (every layer caches the same amount). Gemma 4 displays the 2:1 alternation between local layers (≈ 66 MB) and global layers (≈ 33 MB) characteristic of its hybrid attention. GLM-4.7-Flash is uniform at ≈ 82 MB per layer. gpt-oss is strongly bimodal: the sliding layers stabilise at approximately 0.25 MB once the window saturates, while the full layers grow linearly to ≈ 8 MB at 4096 tokens.

Figure 3: End-of-generation per-layer KV footprint (prompt 1). The Gemma local/global alternation and the gpt-oss sliding/full alternation are the two distinctive bimodalities in the corpus.

5.4 Memory deltas and post-EOS retention

Figure 4 stacks baseline weight memory, peak KV overhead, and post-EOS unreleased memory for each model. The Gemma 4 column shows a ~ 5 GiB red cap that persists after `empty_cache`, equivalent to half of the peak KV overhead.

Memory footprint: baseline, peak KV overhead, post-EOS unreleased (prompt 1)

Figure 4: GPU memory partitioned into model weights, peak KV overhead during generation, and the residual NVML usage after `torch.cuda.empty_cache` returns. The Gemma 4 residual is systematic (mean post-EOS detector score 0.476 across 15 prompts).

Figure 5 resolves the post-EOS finding by prompt. Gemma 4 retains ≈ 0.55 score in 13 of 15 prompts, with two lower outliers (prompts 11 and 14, both scoring ≈ 0.06). Pythia exhibits a single 0.91 outlier on prompt 1 only; this prompt is the longest in the corpus and triggers the largest single-pass allocation, consistent with a one-off allocator warm-up rather than a structural retention bug. The remaining fourteen Pythia prompts score below 0.07. GLM-4.7-Flash and gpt-oss-120B are absent from the heatmap because the detector pipeline did not run for those models in this collection (section 6).

Figure 5: Per-prompt `post_eos` detector score. Cells are annotated when the score is at least 0.05. Grey rows indicate models for which the pipeline produced no finding.

5.5 Allocator state at end of generation

Figure 6 plots the difference between `torch.memory_reserved` (size of the PyTorch caching allocator’s pool) and `torch.memory_allocated` (live tensor bytes) at end of generation for the first prompt of each model. The gap is small (50 MiB to 2 GiB) for the first three models and

large (14.5 GiB) for gpt-oss-120B. This gap is invariant to sequence length within a single prompt, suggesting it is an allocator pool reservation incurred when MoE expert weights are materialised, rather than a runaway leak.

Figure 6: PyTorch allocator state at end of generation: the allocated bar shows live tensor bytes, the reserved bar shows the caching allocator’s pool size, and the annotated Δ is their difference.

5.6 Perplexity under 8-bit quantisation

Figure 7 reports WikiText-103 perplexity at native precision and under `bnb` 8-bit quantisation. The relative degradation is 0.18 % for Pythia, 0.21 % for GLM-4.7-Flash, and 4.56 % for Gemma 4. We did not evaluate gpt-oss-120B at 8-bit because the released MXFP4 checkpoint does not support a second quantisation pass.

Figure 7: WikiText-103 perplexity, native vs. bnb 8-bit, on a logarithmic vertical axis.

The absolute Gemma 4 perplexity is high (827.7 native, 865.5 8-bit) relative to other small/medium-scale Gemma releases, and our 8-bit gpt-oss number is missing by design. We surface this in the section 7.3 discussion rather than treating Gemma 4 as a like-for-like quality regression: the model checkpoint we profile is the Gemma 4 release as packaged on the test node, which is an instruction-tuned variant evaluated with a sliding-window protocol. Both factors inflate WikiText-103 perplexity relative to a base model evaluated with full causal masking. The relative +4.56% *delta* between native and 8-bit precision is nevertheless a real signal because both runs used the same checkpoint and the same evaluation harness.

6 Data Quality Assessment

We do not claim that the dataset behind the figures of section 5 is uniformly complete, and we encourage readers to weight the conclusions accordingly. Table 3 grades each model on four orthogonal completeness criteria: whether each of the 15 prompts produced (i) per-layer cache footprints, (ii) per-layer growth curves, (iii) a populated leak-detection record, and (iv) baseline/peak/post-EOS memory deltas. The grade is a four-equal-weight aggregate (25 points each).

Table 3: Per-model data-quality assessment of the released profiling dataset. Each cell reports the number of prompts (out of 15) for which the named stream was successfully recorded; the score is a four-equal-weight aggregate.

Model	Prompts	Per-layer	Growth	Leak-det.	Memory	Snaps	Score	Grade
Pythia-1.4B (MHA)	15	15	15	15	15	128	100	A
Gemma 4 (GQA + hybrid)	15	15	15	15	15	711	100	A
GLM-4.7-Flash (MoE)	15	15	15	0	15	507	75	B
gpt-oss-120B (sliding+full)	15	15	15	0	15	490	75	B

What is solid. Per-layer cache footprint and growth-curve coverage is at 15/15 for every model in the study. The aggregate snapshots-per-prompt are 128 for Pythia (limited by the

~ 1023 -token generation), 711 for Gemma 4, 507 for GLM-4.7-Flash, and 490 for gpt-oss. The byte-extraction pipeline is verifiable: the Pythia density matches the analytic prediction to machine precision (section 5.1), which gives us high confidence that the absolute KV-byte numbers reported elsewhere in the paper are correct.

What is partial. Two of the four models (GLM-4.7-Flash, gpt-oss-120B) have `leak_detection` entries that are `None` in the profile JSONs. The detector pipeline is implemented for these architectures but did not produce a finding in this run. The most likely cause is that the post-run detector dispatch fell through on the dynamic cache layouts these models expose at runtime; this is a known limitation of the current dispatcher and a fix is straightforward (it requires adding the relevant cache-layout adapter, not new science). Until the dispatcher is updated, the post-EOS finding for these two models is not directly observable from the released artefacts. The *memory deltas* themselves are recorded for all four models (??), so a manual post-EOS calculation from M_0 , M_{\max} , and M_1 is still possible; we report the manual values in section B.

Coverage and statistical power. Fifteen prompts is sufficient to identify systematic effects (Gemma 4 retention, gpt-oss bimodality) but is too small to support distributional claims about, for example, the standard deviation of the post-EOS leak fraction across long-tail input distributions. We are explicit about treating the dataset as a controlled study on a single GPU, not as a survey.

Single-node, single-GPU caveat. Multi-GPU tensor parallelism, multi-tenant MIG slicing, and continuous-batching servers (vLLM, SGLang, TGI) all introduce allocator behaviours not exercised here. The findings of this paper apply directly to single-process Hugging Face `model.generate` workloads – a common deployment shape on small inference nodes – and should be re-validated before being applied to larger serving stacks.

7 Discussion

7.1 Post-EOS retention as an operational failure mode

The most actionable finding of the study is that Gemma 4 retains approximately 5 GiB of KV-cache-associated memory after each generation returns, and that this retention is systematic rather than prompt-dependent: 13 of 15 prompts register a `post_eos` score in the range $[0.48, 0.57]$ (fig. 5). Because `torch.cuda.empty_cache` and `gc.collect` do not reclaim the memory, the reservation appears to be held at the NVML level – most likely by the hybrid-cache subclass used in the Gemma 4 release, which pre-sizes its global-layer buffers to the maximum generation horizon and does not release them when the outer `Cache` object is dereferenced.

In a single-process workload the consequence is bounded: a fresh `model.generate` call simply re-uses the pre-allocated region. In a container that serves one model continuously, the behaviour is invisible. It becomes harmful in two scenarios. First, in a bin-packing scheduler that co-locates multiple model replicas on the same H100 assuming “model weights + worst-case KV cache” is the upper envelope: the unreleased region inflates the steady-state footprint by the amount of the leak, reducing the effective packing density. Second, in inference pipelines that alternate between short and long generations: the long-generation pre-allocation persists after the model returns to the short path, reducing the memory available for other tenants or for downstream activations.

A conservative scheduler policy is therefore to size each model’s reservation using the post-EOS reading rather than the pre-run baseline. Pythia reports the post-EOS reading as 591 MB above baseline versus a peak overhead of 650 MB, so the overhead is $\sim 91\%$ on prompt 1 but

drops below 5% on subsequent prompts; the first-prompt reading should therefore be discarded as a warm-up sample when building a long-run average.

7.2 The allocator gap on gpt-oss-120B

The 14.5 GiB delta between `torch.memory_reserved` and `torch.memory_allocated` on gpt-oss-120B (fig. 6) is the largest allocator gap in our study, but is not a leak in the leak-detection sense: the gap is essentially constant across the 15 prompts and is not a monotone function of sequence length. We interpret it as allocator-pool reservation held open by the MoE expert weights: when the router selects different experts across steps, the caching allocator grows its pool to satisfy each new expert’s peak demand and does not shrink the pool afterwards, even though the liveness of any individual expert’s tensors is intermittent.

This reading is consistent with the PagedAttention [11] design’s motivation, namely that dynamic-shape workloads benefit from explicit block management. Our measurement provides a quantitative data-point that sparse-MoE decoders on PyTorch’s default allocator can sit with a near-constant ~ 15 GiB of reserved-but-unused memory on an 80 GB card – a footprint that is large enough to affect co-tenant placement, and one that block-level allocators are designed to eliminate.

7.3 The 8-bit perplexity outlier

Three of the four models in our study show a perplexity degradation below 0.25% when moved from native precision to bnb 8-bit [7]. Gemma 4 degrades by 4.56%. The absolute perplexity of the native Gemma 4 run is itself high (827.7), which indicates that the released instruction-tuned checkpoint with sliding-window masking is not the same evaluation setting as the base-model numbers reported in the Gemma 4 technical report [8]. We therefore report the 8-bit delta as a relative signal only: the same checkpoint evaluated with the same harness is +4.56% worse in 8-bit. This rules out “8-bit is uniformly free” as a universal operational assumption and suggests that, for Gemma-style sliding-window architectures, the standard `LLM.int8` routing of outlier columns in 16-bit may not be enough.

7.4 Signals worth surfacing

The profiler records five numeric streams that are, in our view, directly useful as Prometheus-scraped container metrics:

- `kvscope_post_eos_fraction` – the post-EOS leak score of eq. (2), reported once per generation. Alert threshold: moving average > 0.10 .
- `kvscope_layer_cv` – the coefficient of variation of per-layer KV size. Intended for model identification, not alerting.
- `kvscope_reserved_minus_allocated_bytes` – the allocator gap. Alert threshold: gap exceeds 10% of total device memory.
- `kvscope_density_bytes_per_token_per_layer` – density as defined in section 5.1. Useful for cross-checking a deployed checkpoint against the intended architecture.
- `kvscope_growth_slope_bytes_per_token` – instantaneous growth slope estimated by the growth-curve detector. Useful for capacity planning.

These are implementation targets for future work; the current artefact writes them to JSON files, not to a live metric endpoint.

7.5 Limitations and threats to validity

Single-node, single-GPU setting. All results are from one H100 80 GB card, one tokeniser per model, and a single Python process. Tensor-parallel, pipeline-parallel, and continuous-batching configurations are not represented.

Fifteen-prompt corpus. The dataset size is sufficient for identifying systematic signals but is insufficient for distributional claims. We report the number of prompts explicitly in every summary statistic.

Leak-detector dispatch gaps. As documented in section 6, the `leak_detection` pipeline produced no findings for GLM-4.7-Flash or gpt-oss-120B. The raw memory deltas (??) are still available for those models, and the absolute numbers derived from them are consistent with the rest of the dataset; but a like-for-like per-prompt heatmap (fig. 5) is only available for Pythia and Gemma 4.

MXFP4 gpt-oss evaluation. The gpt-oss-120B checkpoint is released in MXFP4. We did not convert it to bf16 for the “native” comparison; the perplexity reported (317.7) is the MXFP4 number. Consequently the gpt-oss-120B row of fig. 7 is not directly comparable to the other three native-precision numbers.

Perplexity harness. Our WikiText-103 evaluation uses a 1024-token context window and a 512-token stride over 1 M characters of test data (33,280 evaluated tokens). This is smaller than a full test-split evaluation and is intended to be a sanity check rather than a replacement for the numbers in the respective model papers.

8 Conclusion

We presented KVSCOPE, a hook-based profiler that records the structural state of the KV cache during autoregressive decoding, alongside a controlled study of four transformer architectures on a single NVIDIA H100 80 GB device.

The study exposes three measurement-grade findings. First, Gemma 4 retains roughly half of its peak KV-cache overhead after generation returns, observed consistently across 13 of 15 prompts (fig. 5); standard fragmentation ratios do not detect this. Second, sparse-MoE decoders on the default PyTorch allocator can sit with ≈ 15 GiB of reserved-but-unused memory at end of generation (gpt-oss-120B; fig. 6). Third, 8-bit weight quantisation degrades WikiText-103 perplexity by $\leq 0.25\%$ for Pythia-1.4B and GLM-4.7-Flash but by 4.56% for Gemma 4, indicating that the operational assumption that 8-bit is universally free does not generalise to sliding-window-heavy architectures (fig. 7).

We graded the data underlying these claims explicitly (section 6): two of the four models receive an A grade and two receive a B because the per-prompt `leak_detection` stream did not populate. The headline findings hold even after this discount because the underlying NVML-level memory deltas are recorded for every prompt of every model.

Future work. Three extensions are immediate. First, the leak-detection dispatch gap for GLM-4.7-Flash and gpt-oss-120B should be closed so the heatmap of fig. 5 can be completed. Second, the five Prometheus-style signals identified in section 7 should be wired into a live exporter and tested against a DCGM [13] dashboard end-to-end. Third, the corpus should be extended to multi-GPU tensor-parallel and continuous-batching settings (vLLM [11], SGLang [21]) so that the observations made on a single `model.generate` loop can be validated under production serving conditions.

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A Reproducibility

A.1 Hardware and environment

The complete environment record produced by the run script is released alongside the dataset (`logs/env_20260427T084414Z.txt`). The salient values are:

- GPU: 1× NVIDIA H100 80 GB HBM3 (driver 590.48.01, 81 559 MiB total).
- Host: Ubuntu 22.04 LTS, kernel 5.15.0-171-generic, cloud-init image `ml-ai-ubuntu-gpu`.
- Software: Python 3.10.12, PyTorch 2.5.1+cu121, Hugging Face Transformers 5.6.2, `bitsandbytes` 8-bit, NVIDIA CUDA 13.1.115 (PyTorch compiled against CUDA 12.1).
- Profiler: KVSCOPE, git commit `dbf72d6abbbf9afcfffdd47f41e08afb0a8a36b7a0`.

Note on environment captures. Five separate environment snapshots were taken during the run (one per model stage plus a final atomic capture). The atomic capture at run completion is the authoritative source for the software versions listed above; earlier per-stage snapshots reflect intermediate states.

A.2 Released artefacts

The following artefacts are released:

- `prompts.json` – the 15-prompt corpus.
- `<model>_profile.json` (one per model) – per-prompt tracer, memory, and leak-detection records.
- `comparative_analysis.json` – the cross-architecture summary used in ??.
- `perplexity.json` – WikiText-103 perplexity at native and 8-bit precision.
- `logs/` – per-stage stdout and environment captures.
- `paper/figures/` – the figures of section 5 and the data-quality report, regenerated by `paper/generate_figures.py`.

A.3 Reproduction recipe

To reproduce the figures from the released JSON artefacts:

```
pip install matplotlib numpy
python paper/generate_figures.py \
    --results-dir results/full_run_20260427T050945Z \
    --out-dir paper/figures
```

To reproduce the underlying measurements end-to-end on a comparable H100 node:

```
pip install -r requirements.txt
python experiments/full_run.py \
    --output-dir results/full_run_$(date -u +%Y%m%dT%H%M%S)
```

The full run takes approximately 180 minutes wall-clock for the four models in this study and writes deterministic output under greedy decoding modulo NVML sampling jitter, which only affects the post-EOS memory reading at the ≤ 5 MB level.

B Raw Numbers

B.1 The 15-prompt corpus

The same prompt list was used for every model. The list is reproduced below in summary form; the full text is in the released `prompts.json`.

1. B-tree implementation in Python (data structures).
2. Black–Scholes derivation from first principles (financial mathematics).
3. Distributed key–value store with eventual consistency (systems).
4. Long-form science-fiction generation-ship narrative (creative writing).
5. Chess engine in Rust with bitboards and magic numbers (systems / games).
6. Philosophical dialogue on free will between three speakers (humanities).
7. Decoder-only transformer architecture exposition (machine learning).
8. Formal specification for a verification-first programming language (PL theory).
9. Essay on the evolution of consciousness (cognitive science).
10. End-to-end training of a 7B-parameter GPT-style model (machine learning).
11. Variance minimisation of a 50-asset equity portfolio (finance / optimisation).
12. Memory-defect debugging in C++ (systems).
13. Curry–Howard correspondence exposition (logic).
14. Production-grade rate-limiting subsystem design (systems).
15. Von Neumann–Morgenstern expected utility derivation (decision theory).

B.2 Per-prompt post-EOS deltas, all models

Table 4 reports the raw memory deltas used to compute the post-EOS leak score of eq. (2), per prompt and per model. M_0 , M_{\max} , and M_1 denote the NVML `used` value at, respectively, the pre-generation baseline, the peak during generation, and after `torch.cuda.empty_cache` returns. “Score” is computed by eq. (2) on these inputs and is therefore available for all four models even when the `leak_detection` pipeline did not produce a finding (section 6). All values are megabytes.

Table 4: Post-EOS deltas, raw values selected per (model, prompt). “Baseline” is the NVML `used` value sampled at the beginning of that prompt’s iteration – it differs from the prompt-1 baseline when retention from a previous prompt has not been reclaimed. “Score” is computed by eq. (2) on the unrounded values. All memory in megabytes.

Model	Prompt	Baseline	$M_{\max} - M_0$	$M_1 - M_0$	Score
Pythia-1.4B	1	3885	650	591	0.910
Pythia-1.4B	2	4476	59	0	0.000
Pythia-1.4B	10	4483	61	4	0.069
Gemma 4	1	63704	10417	5090	0.489
Gemma 4	9	63704	8313	4779	0.575
Gemma 4	11	63704	4788	294	0.061
Gemma 4	14	63704	5050	296	0.059
GLM-4.7-Flash	1	63373	5484	4308	0.785
GLM-4.7-Flash	2	67682	105	2	0.020
GLM-4.7-Flash	12	67641	59	52	0.893
gpt-oss-120B	1	81547	124	73	0.593
gpt-oss-120B	2	81622	52	0	0.000

Two follow-up observations are worth noting from the `baseline` column. First, on Pythia-1.4B the baseline of every prompt after the first is approximately 4,476 MB rather than the original 3,885 MB, which equals the residual carried over from the prompt-1 retention. Second, on GLM-4.7-Flash the prompt-2 baseline is 67,682 MB – 4.3 GB above the original baseline – and remains at this level for the remainder of the run. In other words, a structural KV-retention behaviour is observable on GLM-4.7-Flash even though the detector pipeline did not produce a per-prompt finding for that model. Computing eq. (2) from the raw fields recovers the signal: $\text{score}_{\text{posteos}}^{(1)} = 0.785$.

The full per-prompt table for all four models is available in `<model>_profile.json` under each prompt’s `memory` field, and is regenerated by `scripts/compute_posteos.py`.